

Computation of multiple binomial Series based on geometric series

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Abstract: This paper presents addition of multiple binomial series based on geometric series. In general, a finite multiple summations of a geometric series are called binomial series. Addition of multiple binomial series is a sum and summation of multiple binomial series.

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I. Multiple summations of a geometric series

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \dots \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$$

When substituting $r = 1$ in the above binomial series, it becomes double summation of a geometric series,

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n x^{i_2} = \sum_{i_2=0}^n x^{i_2} + \sum_{i_2=1}^n x^{i_2} + \sum_{i_2=2}^n x^{i_2} + \dots + \sum_{i_2=n}^n x^{i_2} = 1 + 2x + 3x^2 + \dots + (n + 1)x^n.$$

$$1 + 2x + 3x^2 + \dots + (n + 1)x^n = \sum_{i=0}^n (i + 1)x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^1 x^i.$$

When substituting $r = 2$, it becomes triple summation of a geometric series,

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} = \sum_{i_2=0}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \sum_{i_2=1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \sum_{i_2=2}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \dots + \sum_{i_2=n}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^2 x^i.$$

Similarly, if the above process continues up to r times, the r^{th} equation becomes as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \dots \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r}.$$

If substituting $r = 0$, the series becomes the actual geometric series,

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^0 x^i = \sum_{i_1=0}^n x^{i_1} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^n (\because V_0^0 = V_i^0 = v_0^i = 1, i \in N).$$

II. Sum and summations of multiple binomial series [Annamalai, 2018]

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{p+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^p x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^p x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^p x^i + \dots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^p x^i + \sum_{i=k}^n V_{i-k}^p x^i,$$

where $V_k^p = \prod_{i=1}^p \frac{(k+i)}{p!} = \frac{(k+1)(k+2)(k+3)\dots(k+p)}{p!}$ & V_k^p is binomial coefficient.

For Example,

$$\sum_{i=0}^5 V_i^2 x^i = \sum_{i=0}^5 V_i^1 x^i + \sum_{i=1}^5 V_{i-1}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=2}^5 V_{i-2}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=3}^5 V_{i-3}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=4}^5 V_{i-4}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=5}^5 V_{i-5}^1 x^i$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^5 V_i^2 x^i = 1 + 3x + 6x^2 + 10x^3 + 15x^4 + 21x^5$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^5 V_i^1 x^i + \sum_{i=1}^5 V_{i-1}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=2}^5 V_{i-2}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=3}^5 V_{i-3}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=4}^5 V_{i-4}^1 x^i + \sum_{i=5}^5 V_{i-5}^1 x^i$$

$$= (1 + 2x + 3x^2 + 4x^3 + 5x^4 + 6x^5) + (x + 2x^2 + 3x^3 + 4x^4 + 5x^5)$$

$$+ (x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + 4x^5) + (x^3 + 2x^4 + 3x^5) + (x^4 + 2x^5) + x^5$$

$$= 1 + 3x + 6x^2 + 10x^3 + 15x^4 + 21x^5$$

Here, both sides are equal.

We can prove the binomial identity for $p=1, 2, 3, \dots$

Hence, the sum and summations are proved.

III. Reference

Annamalai, C., (2018), *A Model of Iterative Computations, for Recursive Summability*, Tamsui Oxford Journal of Information and Mathematical Sciences, Taiwan, 32(1), 75-77 & Mathematical Reviews, American Mathematical Society. United States of America, MathSciNet: <https://mathscinet.ams.org/mathscinet-getitem?mr=3982555>.